

Early mungbean cultivars for intensive cropping before rainfed wetland rice in the Philippines

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About 57% of the total Philippine rice crop is rainfed wetland (including some nonbunded dryland fields); only about 43% is irrigated. The rainfed wetland rice areas are generally planted to a single crop of rice, although some areas grow a second crop with low management. Most of the research to intensify cropping and production of rainfed wetland rice is concentrated on the introduction of additional crops (e.g. rice, mungbean, cowpea, soybean, sorghum, and

vegetables) to follow the first rice crop. The few attempts to grow upland crops before rainfed wetland rice have shown mungbean to be most promising. Other promising crops are sesame, bush sitao, and green corn.

Ten promising early-maturing mung bean cultivars were evaluated for adaptability to intensive cropping before rainfed wetland bunded rice in replicated trials at IRRI and at outreach sites in Manaoag (Pangasinan Province), and Oton (Iloilo Province). The trials were planted with high tillage in late April to early May and harvested 60-64 days later. The farmers' local variety served as the check, but at IRRI the variety CES87 was used. Yields for all locations averaged 1.1 t/ha – 144% higher than the Philippine national yield average of 450 kg/ha. CES ID-21 (released by the Philippine Seedboard as Pag-asa) yielded

significantly the highest, followed by M350 (1.4 and 1.2 t/ha). Average yield was highest in Los Baños (1.4 t/ha) and lowest in Pangasinan (0.8 t/ha). The average number of days to maturity ranged from 60 to 64 days after emergence. H70-16, a selection from Burma, was the earliest; M350, CES 1K-CES 1K-25Y, and Dau Mo were the latest. CES ID-21 matures in 63 days (see table). It is resistant to *Cercospora* leaf spot disease and has short plant type. Multiple regression analysis showed that yield was significantly related to maturity, plant height, and disease resistance ($r^2 = 0.65$, $r^2 = 0.66$, and $r^2 = 0.72$). No significant relationship was found between *Cercospora* leaf spot and plant height, indicating that both factors controlled a different component of yield variance. ■

Yield and days to maturity of 11 elite early mungbean cultivars before rainfed wetland bunded rice at 3 Philippine sites, 1979 wet season.^a

Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)				Maturity (days) ^c			
	Los Baños	Iloilo	Pangasinan	Av ^b	Los Baños	Iloilo	Pangasinan	Av
CES ID-21 (Pag-asa)	1.5 a	1.6 a	1.1 a	1.4 a	61 c	66 ab	61 ab	63 ab
M350	1.5 a	1.3 b	0.8 bc	1.2 ab	65 a	66 ab	61 ab	64 a
CES 55	1.5 a	1.3 bcd	0.8 bcd	1.2 ab	61 c	63 c	60 b	61 ab
CES J-2Y	1.5 a	1.1 fg	0.8 b	1.2 ab	61 c	63 c	61 ab	62 ab
EG MG 174-3	1.5 a	1.2 defg	0.8 b	1.1 ab	62 b	64 c	62 ab	63 ab
H70-16	1.5 a	1.2 def	0.6 e	1.0 b	61 c	59 d	60 b	60 b
CES N-6Y	1.4 ab	1.1 fg	0.7 de	1.1 b	61 c	64 c	61 ab	62 ab
Local check ^d	1.5 a	1.0 g	0.5 f	1.0 b	61 c	67 a	61 ab	63 ab
CES 1K-25Y	1.1 bc	1.1 efg	0.7 cd	1.0 b	65 a	66 ab	62 a	64 a
MG 50-10AY	0.9 c	1.3 bc	0.8 bcd	1.0 b	61 c	59 d	66 b	62 ab
Dau Mo	0.9 c	1.2 cde	0.7 de	0.9 b	65 a	66 ab	62 a	64 a
Av	1.4	1.2	0.8	1.1	62	64	61	63
CV (%)	12.6	9.3	15.2	(a) 23.9 (b) 12.2	0.7	1.5	2.0	(a) 2.7 (b) 1.2

^aAny two means having a common letter in a column do not differ significantly at the 5% level. ^bAverage yield and maturity were analyzed using split-plot, with location as the main plot and cultivars as subplots. ^cFrom emergence until harvest. ^dLocal check was CES87 (recommended Philippine Seedboard variety) for IRRI, and farmers' cultivars for Iloilo and Pangasinan.

Announcements

Illustrations for translations of *A farmer's primer on growing rice* available at IRRI

Several national rice improvement programs have requested IRRI's cooperation in the translation and local printing of *A farmer's primer on growing rice*.

Therefore, IRRI is providing black-and-white prints of all illustrations and artwork in the 221-page manual, with all English text blocked out, to rice agencies interested in publishing local editions. Translations of the text can be added to the illustrations and reproduced by offset printing.

The cost is US\$16/set (actual reproduction cost plus one copy of the primer plus airmail postage).

The book answers questions such as why a farmer incubates seed, why he or she applies fertilizer, or how and when that fertilizer should be incorporated. *A farmer's primer* was designed to help